

Synthesis of Disperse Dyes and their Application on Polyester Fibre

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Several monoazo dyes from 2-aminobenzothiazole have been reported¹. These dyes produce bright scarlet to red-violets of high tinctorial power and excellent dischargeability. Hence it was thought interesting to undertake synthesis and study the dyeing properties of the azo dyes based on 2-amino-4-methylthiazole system.

Results and Discussion

2-Amino-4-methylthiazole was diazotised and coupled with various coupling components, such as *m*-chloro-*N,N*-bis- β -hydroxyethylaniline, *m*-chloro-*N,N*-bis- β -acetoxyethylaniline, *N,N*-bis- β -hydroxyethyl-*m*-toluidine, *N,N*-bis- β -acetoxyethyl-*m*-toluidine, *N,N*-bis- β -hydroxyethylaniline, 3-*N,N*-bis- β -acetoxyethylamino-4-methoxyacetanilide, 3-*N*- β -cyanoethyl-*N*- β -hydroxyethylamino-4-methoxyacetanilide, *N*- β -acetoxyethyl-*N*- β -cyanoethylaniline, *N*- β -cyanoethyl-*N*- β -hydroxyethylaniline, *N*- β -cya-

noethyl-*N*-ethylaniline and *m-N,N*-diethylaminoacetanilide, to give dyes D-1 to D-11 respectively. These dyes were applied to polyester fibre and their dyeing and fastness properties were evaluated (Table 1).

Some dyes have good substantivity for polyester, exhausting well to give bright dyeings of good fastness to washing, perspiration and rubbing. Their light fastness is generally better. The outstanding property of the thiazolylazo dyes is their high sublimation fastness or resistance to staining of undyed fabric when dyeing are heated. The nature of the substituents in the coupling components has a large influence on the resistance to sublimation. In most cases, substituents can improve the sublimation fastness. The acetyl group confers the highest degree of resistance to sublimation. However, the methoxy group confers higher resistance to sublimation.

TABLE 1

Dye no.	Colour	λ_{max} nm	R_t	<i>K/S</i>	Exhaustion %	Light fastness	Wash fastness	Perspiration fastness		Rubbing fastness		Sublimation fastness °C
								Acid	Alkali	Dry	Wet	
D-1	Light pink	314	0.73	0.57	58.50	5	5	5	5	5	5	140
D-2	Light pink	311	0.75	0.51	56.50	5	5	5	5	3-4	4	170
D-3	Pink	380	0.77	0.53	65.00	5	5	5	5	5	5	140
D-4	Light pink	320	0.77	0.56	67.00	5	5	5	5	5	5	170
D-5	Violet-red	553	0.81	0.47	68.13	5	5	5	5	5	4	140
D-6	Grey	570	0.84	0.54	71.25	5	5	5	5	5	4-5	180
D-7	Light brown	480	0.83	0.52	63.37	5	5	5	5	4-5	4	160
D-8	Light orange	470	0.80	0.48	58.50	5	5	5	5	3-4	3-4	160
D-9	Light green	580	0.79	0.49	56.50	5	5	5	5	4	5	140
D-10	Light green	575	0.78	0.44	61.25	5	5	5	5	5	5	140
D-11	Light brown	475	0.82	0.45	67.50	5	5	5	5	5	5	150

R, R¹ = β -acetoxy ethyl, β -cyanoethyl,
 β -hydroxyethyl, ethyl

R² = H, methoxy

R³ = H, acetamido, chloro, methyl

Experimental

2-Amino-4-methylthiazole : To a suspension of thiourea (0.1 mol) in acetone (0.2 mol) was added liquid bromine (0.05 mol) dropwise in 0.5 h, with continuous stirring and the mixture was then refluxed for 2 h in a water-bath. The resulting product was boiled with water (50 ml) and treated with ammonia to liberate the base which was crystallised from 50% ethanol, (78%), m.p. 45–46°.

Diazotisation of 2-amino-4-methylthiazole : To a suspension of 2-amino-4-methylthiazole (0.05 mol) in water (20 ml), concentrated HCl (65 ml) was added dropwise. The clear solution obtained was cooled to 0–5° in an ice-bath. A solution of NaNO₂ (0.05 mol) in water (13 ml) at 0°, was added to it dropwise and stirred for 1 h at 0–5° (with positive test for nitrous acid). The clear diazo solution was used for subsequent coupling reaction.

Coupling of diazo solution with various coupling components : To the coupling component (0.05 mol) suspended in water (20 ml), concentrated HCl (6.5 ml) was added with stirring. The solution was then cooled (5°) and the diazo solution was added to it dropwise with stirring maintaining neutral pH by addition of Na₂CO₃ solution and stirred for 3 h at 0–5°. The resulting solid was dried and purified from DMF-chloroform to yield the products (57–73%) : D-1, m.p. 71°; D-2, 72°; D-3, 78°; D-4, 65°; D-5, 77°; D-6, 68°; D-7, 73°; D-8, 87°; D-9, 80°; D-10, 82°; D-11, 88°.

Application. 2% shade on polyester : Material and condition of the experiment were as follows : weight of fabric, 2 g; amount of dye, 40 g; dispersing agent, dadamol, 40 mg; Tween-80, 5

mg; MLR, 1 : 50; pH, 4.0; temp., 130°; time, 60 min; total volume of dye bath, 100 ml. The pH for the disperse dyes was adjusted with CH₃COOH. The sample of fabric was introduced in the dye-bath and the temperature was slowly raised to 130° in 30 min. The dye-bath was then cooled. The fabric was removed and stirred in water, squeezed and rinsed with water and squeezed.

2-(Substituted-4-*N,N*-dialkylaminophenyl)azo-4-methylthiazole dyes were separated on tlc using chloroform-methanol (95 : 5) solvent system. The *R_f* values are given in Table 1. Absorption maxima (λ_{\max}) were determined in DMF at 28° using a Hitachi V-3200 spectrophotometer at 2×10^{-3} M dye concentration : ν_{\max} 1 360, 1 485 (C=N of thiazole), 1 585 (N=N), 1 725 (C=O), 1 240, 1 400 cm⁻¹ (O-H bend and C-O stretch) and 765 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); pmr δ (DMSO-d₆) of dye D-2, 1.99 (3H, CH₃), 2.57 (6H, 2 \times COOCH₃), 3.66 (4H, 2 \times CH₂, β to OCOCH₃), 3.82 (4H, 2 \times CH₂, α to OCOCH₃), 6.71 (H, ethylenic proton of thiazole), 7.15 (3H, ArH); D-4, δ 1.99 (3H, CH₃), 2.26 (3H, Ar-CH₃), 2.59 (6H, 2 \times COCH₃), 3.81 (4H, 2 \times CH₂, β to OCOCH₃), 4.08 (4H, 2 \times CH₂, α to OCOCH₃), 6.71 (1H, ethylenic proton of thiazole), 7.17 (3H, ArH).

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References

- 1 M. F. SARTORI, *J. Soc. Dyers Colour*, 1967, **83**, 144; Y NOBORU, K TOSHIO, U. HIROJI, M HISAMICHI and O ICHIRO, Jap Pat. 7 546 958/1975 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1975, **83**, 149085), R. HALN and C. MULER, Fr Pat 1 574 372/1679 (*Chem Abstr.* 1970, **73**, 57146); ICI Ltd, Fr Pat. 1 543 298/1968 (*Chem Abstr.*, 1970, **73**, 99993), Y. NOBORU, K TOSHIO, U. HIROJI, M HISAMICHI and O. ICHIRO, Jap. Pat. 7 546 984/1975 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1975, **83**, 149086).